

Modelling the range expansion of pumpkinseed *Lepomis gibbosus* across Europe, with a special focus on Ukraine and Latvia

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Abstract. Freshwater ecosystems are exceptionally vulnerable to biological invasions. The introduction of non-native species of fish to Europe has been a common practice, including the introduction of the North American pumpkinseed, *Lepomis gibbosus*. The range expansion of this species has continued across the continent, with new areas occupied in Ukraine. Using a species distribution modelling approach, predictions are made of the geographic range of the fish based on presence records and environmental variables from the Near-global environmental information for freshwater ecosystems database likely to be associated with habitat suitability and important for the possible further expansion of *L. gibbosus*. Results show the current widespread distribution of *L. gibbosus* in Ukraine and prospects for future expansion of the species into Belarus and the Baltic countries. In Latvia, at the potential range edge of *L. gibbosus*, chances for a spontaneous invasion are relatively low.

Keywords: *Lepomis gibbosus*, invasive species, species distribution modelling, climate change, Ukraine, Latvia.

Introduction

Dispersal of species beyond their native range is a profound driver of global change. The advent of globalization has increasingly led to the anthropogenic removal of dispersal barriers with the rapid increase in the translocation of organisms (Early et al. 2016). Besides human-facilitated movements of invasive biological organisms, climate change also plays a significant role in determining invasion success (Walther et al. 2009, Fletcher 2018). Climate change may lead to range expansions and/or range shifts of organisms, particularly at range edges, where conditions were previously of marginal suitability and may now rapidly become suitable (Dukes & Mooney 1999). In the same way, existing populations of seemingly harmless introduced species may outperform native species and become invasive under novel climatic regimes (Stachowicz et al. 2002, Pupina et al. 2018, Nekrasova et al. 2021a, 2021b, 2022). Such changes in species distributions may lead to novel biotic interactions with unexpected outcomes, some of which may mean loss of biodiversity or ecosystem services (Schweiger et al. 2010, Kuybida et al. 2019).

Freshwater ecosystems provide societies with valuable goods and services yet are disproportionately vulnerable to biological invasions compared to terrestrial systems (Moorhouse & McDonald 2015). Introduced non-native species, particularly fishes, can cause considerable impacts on freshwater ecosystems (Copp et al. 2017). For alien fish in Europe, there is a list of at least 40 established species, excluding fish species without self-sustaining populations (van der Veer & Nentwig 2015). The pumpkinseed *Lepomis gibbosus* is a North American sunfish (Centrarchidae) introduced to Europe in the late 19th century for recreational angling and as an ornamental fish for estate ponds. Nowadays, the species is established in at least 28 countries across Europe and Asia Minor; however, it is considered invasive in part but not all of its introduced range (Copp & Fox 2007). Currently, the species is not considered to spread

to more northerly latitudes (the northernmost known reproducing population is situated in southern Norway); however, *L. gibbosus* is predicted to become invasive to these areas under conditions of climate warming (Rahel & Olden 2008, Britton et al. 2010). While more than a century has passed since its initial introduction to Europe, the range expansion of this fish species has continued across the continent (Yavno et al. 2020). Exploring limiting environmental factors may help to understand the key drivers of the suggested range expansion of the species. It may also help establish efficient monitoring programs, including risk assessments of *L. gibbosus* invasion. Our objective was to predict the geographic range of the fish based on presence records and environmental variables likely to be associated with habitat suitability and important for the possible further expansion of *L. gibbosus*. Thus, the findings of this study can inform enhanced surveillance efforts in Latvia and Ukraine, where *L. gibbosus* has not yet been recorded but where the environment appears to be favorable for establishment (Tytar et al. 2021). The basic approach applied here is based on species distribution models (SDMs), often also called ecological niche models (ENMs), where species' presences or absences are correlated with environmental variables prevailing in the respective locations to project the potential distribution of a species under current and/or future climatic conditions (Nekrasova et al. 2019). These projections are based on statistical and/or machine learning algorithms to best estimate this species-environment relationship.

Material and Methods

Occurrence data was collected from GBIF (2021, <https://www.gbif.org/species/2394486>), FishBase (2022), and for Ukraine, focused particularly on collecting data from social networking sites, microblogs, and media sharing services, which support textual and visual content and geotagging. These sites include social media platforms such as

Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and Flickr, where users share content in private networks or publicly online (Toivonen et al. 2019, Nekrasova et al. 2022). Social media mining is useful for social and biological research (Monkman et al. 2018). Search queries included Latin and vernacular names of the fish species in Ukrainian and Russian. Data indicative of fish presence were extracted and then georeferenced; photos had to be geo-tagged so that a location was evident. The fish species was found in 17 regions ('oblasts') of Ukraine: Zakarparska, Lvivska, Ivano-Frankivska, Zhytomyrska, Kyivska, Vinnytska, Cherkaska, Poltavska, numerous records came from Dnipropetrovska, Kirovogradska, Zaporizska, Donetska, Luhanska, Khersonska, Mykolaivska, Odeska regions, and Crimea, according to a number of authors (Berg 1949, Diripasko et al. 2008, Fedonenko & Marenkov 2013, Demchenko & Demchenko 2015, Afanasyev et al. 2017, Kutsok et al. 2021, Tytar et al. 2021) and data from social networks (accessed 2008-2020).

Occurrence points varied in spatial density due to variable sampling intensity over geography. As a result, and to avoid overemphasizing heavily on sampled area, we selected points for model calibration using a subsampling regime to reduce sampling bias and spatial autocorrelation, which would produce models of lower rather than higher quality. We used the 'spThin' package in R (Aiello-Lammens et al. 2015) to subsample our dataset such that all occurrence records were separated by a minimum distance that would reduce spatial autocorrelation among model pseudo-residuals to Moran's $I < 0.3$. Moran's I is a widely used measure of spatial autocorrelation, ranging from 0 to 1, with values > 0.3 considered relatively large (Lichstein et al. 2002).

We selected the Near-global environmental information for freshwater ecosystems as a source of the environmental variables (Domisch et al. 2015). The dataset consists of near-global, spatially continuous, and freshwater-specific environmental variables summarizing the upstream environment (climate, topography, land cover, surface geology, and soil) to each grid cell using various metrics (average, minimum, maximum, range). Monthly climate variables are summarized into 19 long-term climatic variables following the "bioclim" framework (Fick & Hijmans 2017).

Considering that the collinearity among environmental variables may lead to overfitting, we used the following measures to reduce the number of variables. Firstly, using Spearman rank correlation coefficients in the 'caret' R package (Kuhn 2008), we eliminated variables with the highest and most significant correlation coefficients ($|r| > 0.8$ and $p < 0.001$). Then, 'Boruta', one of the most effective feature selection algorithms implemented in R, was used to select variables according to their relative importance in distinguishing between presences and absences (Kursa et al. 2010). Instead of true absences, we used pseudo-absence points randomly generated within a bounding box encompassing *L. gibbosus* presence points by employing the 'dismo' R package (Hijmans et al. 2011).

In this paper, we employed two machine learning algorithms, Maxent (Phillips et al. 2006), which has proven good performance and accuracy for such studies (Elith et al. 2011), and Bayesian additive regression trees (BART), a fairly new approach to solving ecological problems and building SDMs (Carlson 2020). Both only need presence data besides the environmental layers.

As part of their output, both methods rank the environmental layers used to train the SDM based on their relative importance in building the model. Importantly, both also allow the construction of response curves to illustrate the effect of selected variables on habitat suitability. Marginal response curves are particularly interesting, showing how the prediction changes as each environmental variable are varied, keeping all other environmental variables at their average sample value. These response curves consist of the specific environmental variable as the x-axis and, on the y-axis, the predicted probability of suitable conditions ranging from 0 to 1 (or zero to 100%). Upward trends for variables indicate a positive relationship; downward movements represent a negative relationship (Baldwin 2009).

Since Maxent is prone to over-fitting, it uses "regularization" (a

beta parameter) to avoid modelling errors when a function corresponds too closely to a particular data set. Higher beta values increase the "smoothness" of species responses to the environment. There is also a choice of an expanded set of transformations of the original covariates (termed features), which help make predictions about the outcome. Maxent fits models using linear, product, quadratic, hinge, and threshold functions, enhancing flexibility for modeling non-linear species-habitat responses. Because Maxent's default regularization parameter and feature classes profoundly impact model performance (Merow et al. 2013), we used the 'SDMtune' package in R (Vignali et al. 2020) to build a series of models with all possible combinations of these parameters. We selected a model with a combination of a feature class and regularization multiplier that provided the best trade-off between model goodness of fit and complexity using the AUC metric (Radosavljevic & Anderson 2014). We used the 10th percentile training presence threshold value to generate contour lines distinguishing suitable for the species areas. This threshold value is considered to provide a better ecologically significant result when compared with more restricted threshold values (Phillips & Dudik 2008).

A final consideration is whether to restrict the model to one based on native range data, data from the invaded range, or include both. This is important because the assumption of niche conservatism (Peterson et al. 1999) under these circumstances is not always met: niches of invasive species can differ from their natives, especially if there has been a long historical distribution of a species in its invaded range, as in the case of *L. gibbosus*. Because the growth and life-history traits of non-native populations of *L. gibbosus* in Europe respond to temperature similarly (Copp & Fox 2007) as native populations (Fox 1994), there is a high chance of finding the niche of the species conserved in the invaded area. Yet species populations often behave differently in invaded ecosystems due to a release from certain predators, competitors, or parasites (Keane & Crawley 2002, Blumenthal 2006). In some cases, models based on data from regions already invaded by a given species are more accurate at forecasting that species' distribution than data from its native range (Loo et al. 2007). Although there is much to be learned from the historical distribution of a species in its native range, only invaded range data incorporate unknown factors such as rapid adaptation and release from predators in forecasting the spread of an invader (Kornis & Vander Zanden 2010). As far as SDMs for invasive species usually focus on climatic variables, partly because climate dominates distributions at the global scale (Elith & Leathwick 2009), we compared both niches in bioclimatic environmental space using an analysis of similarity (ANOSIM) to avoid any bias capable of affecting model transferability. ANOSIM yields significant differences between groups (here: niches) when dissimilarities between groups are larger than dissimilarities within groups. The resulting R-value from an ANOSIM ranges from -1 to 1, with zero indicating random grouping (Oksanen et al. 2018).

Maps of habitat suitability in the GeoTIFF raster format were processed and visualized in SAGA GIS (Conrad et al. 2015). Statistical data were analyzed using the PAST software package (Hammer et al. 2001).

Results

In sum, 1263 and 1386 non-duplicate records were obtained across Europe and North America, respectively. After the thinning procedure, we retained 598 occurrence records for Europe and 873 for North America. By eliminating collinearity and selecting key factors that discriminate areas where *L. gibbosus* is present from those where the species is absent, 18 environmental variables with confirmed mean importance > 10 were selected (Table 1), thus reducing the noise from the data. Each characterizes certain climate

features, topography, land cover, and soil.

An ANOSIM comparison of both niches, native in North America and invaded in Europe, in bioclimatic environmental space, found fairly moderate but statistically significant dissimilarities ($R=0.24$, $p<0.05$) between them. Therefore, only invaded range data was incorporated in the modelling to avoid this bias affecting transferability.

The final models were selected based on fine-tuning employing the AUC value. The best Maxent model used all feature classes (LQPHT) with a regularization multiplier value of 0.8. The ROC curves show 'good' predictive power with AUC scores of 0.895 and 0.874 for the final Maxent and

BART models.

Based on variable importance, both modelling approaches emphasized amongst climate features the importance of the average minimum monthly air temperature for September (tmin9) in producing the SDMs (16.8% contribution, according to Maxent, and 21.0% to BART). Amongst the topography, land cover, and soil features such were the slope range (slope_range) (6.7% and 10.3%, respectively), the maximum percent of urban/built-up area (lc_max9)(10.5% and 20.0%, respectively), and the minimum cation exchange capacity (soil_min7)(4.0% and 19.0%, respectively) (Figs. 1-4).

Table 1. The relative importance of 18 environmental variables from the Near-global environmental information for freshwater ecosystems based on feature selection using the 'Boruta' algorithm

Variable name	Variable explanation	Mean importance (%)
hydro_7	Upstream Temperature Annual Range	17.51
hydro_6	Minimum Upstream Temperature of Coldest Month	16.69
hydro_9	Mean Upstream Temperature of Driest Quarter	16.68
tmin9	Minimum monthly air temperature for September (average)	16.40
lc_max3	Deciduous broadleaf trees (maximum)	15.48
lc_max4	Mixed/other trees (maximum)	12.70
soil_max10	Probability of occurrence (0-100%) of R horizon (maximum)	12.53
lc_av3	Deciduous broadleaf trees (average)	12.37
hydro_19	Upstream Precipitation of Coldest Quarter	12.33
hydro_14	Upstream Precipitation of Driest Month	11.80
soil_av2	Soil pH in H2O (average)	11.70
soil_min7	Cation exchange capacity (minimum)	11.69
slope_range	Slope range	11.66
soil_min1	Soil organic carbon (minimum)	11.49
prec_9	Sum of monthly precipitation September	11.47
hydro_2	Mean Upstream Diurnal Range	11.32
lc_max9	Urban/built-up (maximum)	11.13
tmax6	Maximum monthly air temperature for June (average)	10.73

Figure 1. Marginal response curve for the average minimum monthly air temperature for September (tmin9), [°C] * 10; HS = predicted habitat suitability

Figure 2. Marginal response curve for slope range (slope_range), [°] * 100; HS = predicted habitat suitability

Figure 3. Marginal response curve for urban/built-up area (lc_max_09), [%]; HS = predicted habitat suitability.

Figure 4. Marginal response curve for soil minimum cation exchange capacity (soil_min7), [cmol/kg]; HS = predicted habitat suitability

The obtained probability maps were averaged to produce a habitat suitability map for the pumpkinseed corresponding to the current climate in Europe and clipped to Ukraine and Latvia (Figures 5, 6). Contour lines distinguishing suitable for the species areas match the 10th percentile training presence threshold value.

In our opinion, the map for Ukraine quite closely reflects the current distribution of *L. gibbosus* in the country and prospects for future expansion of the species. Modelling allows us to assume that highly suitable for the species areas (where predicted habitat suitability >0.5) occupy 28% of the country.

Discussion

As mentioned, climatic predictors, in particular monthly variables, were found to be highly important. In the Near-global environmental information dataset for freshwater ecosystems, monthly climate variables are gained from ambient air temperatures. Nevertheless, they have previously been successfully used in models of aquatic species (Kumar et al. 2009, Milanovich et al. 2010, Wenger et al. 2011, Blank & Blaustein 2012) because their values typically correlate with water temperatures (Stefan & Preud'homme 1993). The climatic predictor 'tmin9', found to be highly important, characterizes not only the temperature in September but is closely correlated ($r>0.8$, $p<0.05$) with the average minimum monthly air temperature in April, May, June, July, and August, in other words, characterizes the whole growing season and emphasizes the strong dependence of the well-being of the fish species on temperature. The corresponding marginal response curve illustrates this dependence (Fig. 1), showing low predicted habitat suitability at low temperatures, rapidly increasing with rising temperatures, and gaining a 90% suitability at around 10°C. Such behavior of the curve corroborates with earlier findings. For instance, some Centrarchidae have been

experimentally shown not to feed below 10°C (Marcus 1932). In a field-based study, *L. gibbosus* did not start to feed until the water temperature reached 8.5°C and only reaching the temperature of 9.5°C all fish had moderately full stomachs; prior to this, the stomachs of the fish were shrunken and mucous-filled (Keast 1968). In this way, water temperature is pivotal for meeting the bioenergetic needs of the species, not to mention over-wintering survival.

Considering topography, slope range in relevance to habitat suitability demonstrates a clear downward trend, with higher suitability in places where the difference between the maximum and minimum of the slope barely reaches 20° (Fig. 2). According to the maps visualized in SAGA GIS, these are relatively flat areas found at low altitudes, predominantly (~50%) between zero and 140 m above sea level. Under such circumstances, still waters, whether they be lakes, reservoirs, floodplain lakes or ponds, or marshes, are expected to be widespread and running waters to be of low flow velocity. Previously it was found that increasing altitudes accounted for a lower number of sites with the presence of the pumpkinseed in Slovakia (Jakubcinova et al. 2008) and Portugal mountain rivers and small highland streams, high slope and energy, and low productivity seem to be much less attractive (Ilhéu et al. 2014).

Jakubcinova et al. (2008) consider higher occurrence of the species (together with *Neogobius melanostomus* and *Pseudorasbora parva*) in lower altitudes can be associated with a stronger influence of land use and other human disturbances of which invasive species can take advantage because of their wider environmental tolerances and ability under these circumstances to outcompete more sensitive native species. This notion is supported by the behavior of the marginal response curve showing a general trend of better suitability for *L. gibbosus* in developed areas (Fig. 3). For instance, in the Netherlands, the pumpkinseed is especially abundant in mooreland pools, fish ponds, and urban waters (Van Kleef et al. 2008).

Figure 5. Map of predicted habitat suitability for the pumpkinseed in Ukraine based on the combination of selected predictors from the Near-global environmental information for freshwater ecosystems; the legend shows habitat suitability ranging from high (red) to low (blue); clusters of the species' distribution: 1 - Zakarpatska (Transcarpathia), 2 - Middle (Podol) Dnister, 3 - Lower Danube-Dnister, 4 - Dnister-Lower Dnipro (includes the Southern Boug catchment), 5 - Dnipro Cascade, 6 - Crimea, 7 -Donbas.

Figure 6. Map of predicted habitat suitability for the pumpkinseed in Latvia based on the combination of selected predictors from the Near-global environmental information for freshwater ecosystems; the legend shows habitat suitability ranging from relatively high (red) to low (blue); areas suggested for legal introduction: 1 - Lower Daugava, 2 - Kurzeme Province.

Finally, the upstream soil minimum cation exchange capacity (*soil_min7*) has a significant influence on the physical and chemical properties of the freshwater environment (Fig. 4). Actually, the predictor '*soil_min7*' represents a cluster of intercorrelated soil features such as pH, silt, clay ($r > 0.7$, $p < 0.05$) and sand content (a negative correlation exceeding -0.8 , $p < 0.05$) important for shaping the species' habitat. For instance, there is a preference of female pumpkinseeds for nesting on firm substrates (sand or gravel) as opposed to soft substrates (Danylchuk, Fox 1996). Regarding the pH, the fish can adapt themselves to anything from 6.7 to 8.2 (Bockstael 1984). However, the pumpkinseed is negatively affected when pH drops between 5.2 and 5.3 (Sun & Harvey 1986). From the corresponding marginal

response curve, we can conclude that the species preferred habitat is where values of '*soil_min7*' are below 26 cmol/kg, meaning that under these circumstances, safe levels of pH (> 5.5) are maintained. Less is known about the sand content other than its presence or absence. Under these same circumstances, the preferable minimum sand content mass fraction could be expected to vary between 31.6 and 32.5 percent, but this has yet to be verified.

Initially, the pumpkinseed established itself in Ukraine in the Lower Danube area in lakes Yalpuh and Kahul in 1946 (Berg 1949). In 1952 the species spread to the Dniester Estuary (Diripasko et al. 2008). The modelling shows that the species may have good chances to occupy natural habitats in the Middle Dniester (also referred to as the 'Podol Dniester').

Further upstream expansion into the Carpathian Dniester could be limited by the water flow velocity reaching there a figure of 1 m/s, whereas in the middle and lower course of the river, the corresponding figures are lower, 0.2-0.7 and 0.2-0.4 m/s, respectively (Transboundary ..., 2005).

In 1953 *L. gibbosus* was found to occupy brackish waters in the northwestern corner of the Black Sea (Vinogradov 1960). In 1970 the species extended its range to the Dnieper Estuary (Fedonenko & Marenkov 2013), from where it spread to the lower reaches of the Southern Boug (Movchan 2002, Afanasyev et al. 2017) and set the beginning of the invasion of the reservoirs built upon the Dnieper (the 'Dnieper Cascade'). In the 1970s, a number of fish ponds in Kiev were stocked with pumpkinseed, which had escaped into the wild and presumably laid the source for both up- and downstream invasions. Whatsoever, since 2011 fishermen have been recording the species in their catches from the Kiev Reservoir (Afanasyev et al. 2017). Our modelling shows excellent habitat suitability for *L. gibbosus* throughout the entire cascade of Reservoir on the Dnieper, which likely had accelerated its spread. Moreover, the models predict that the species may move into the Pripyat River as far as Turov in Belarus (347 km from the estuary) and beyond. By the way, this advance could be facilitated by the E40 Inland Waterway (E40 IWW), a transnational project to establish a 2,000 km Black-to-Baltic-Sea inland waterway through Poland, Belarus, and Ukraine connecting the seaports of Gdansk and Kherson, bound for implementation in the coming years.

Further to the south and east, the species is widespread in water bodies of Crimea (appeared since 2002) (Boltachev et al. 2003) and in 2011-2013, reached Lugansk Oblast in the Donbas region (Afanasyev et al. 2017). In the west, the pumpkinseed has been known from the Transcarpathia since 1980 (Fedonenko & Marenkov 2013).

According to the models for Latvia, chances here for the spontaneous invasion of *L. gibbosus* are low: moderately suitable for the species areas (where predicted habitat suitability >0.3) occupy only 3% of the country. Even more, there are no clear geographical corridors that could facilitate such expansion other than brackish waters along the Baltic coast, which in theory, could pave the way to the north. In this respect, the seaside of Kurzeme Province could probably accommodate the species, especially if warmer temperatures will appear together with climate change. If introduced, legally or not, or by accident, the Lower Daugava next to Riga would likely be the most suitable place for the fish.

Traditionally, determining factors driving the distribution of a species would require laborious field measurements of key environmental variables in natural populations or experimental research. However, the advent of GIS and the increased availability of global environmental data in recent years have favored the proliferation of diverse ENMs intended to answer a wide range of applied ecological questions (Peterson et al. 2011). Because these models seek to identify the features that characterize a species' known distribution (their "environmental envelope"), they are likely to provide basic quantitative information about species' apparent habitat preferences (Nakazato et al. 2010). Perhaps most vividly, the extraction of such information has been exemplified by the SDM marginal response curve

generated for the average minimum monthly air temperature for September (Fig. 1) to find the temperature preferences of *L. gibbosus*. Luckily enough, these closely corroborated with findings made earlier in the field. Our modelling shows the current distribution of *L. gibbosus* in Ukraine and prospects for future expansion of the species, particularly into Belarus, where such chances are high. On the contrary, in Latvia, at the potential range edge of *L. gibbosus*, these chances are fairly low, although even today, certain isolated sites offer more or less viable conditions for the species.

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References

- Afanasyev, S.A., Gupalo, Y.A., Manturova, O.V. (2017): Distribution and peculiarities of biology of the pumpkinseed *Lepomis gibbosus* (Perciformes: Centrarchidae) in the water bodies of Kiev City. *Hydrobiological Journal* 53: 14-25.
- Aiello-Lammens, M.E., Boria, R.A., Radosavljevic, A., Vilela, B., Anderson, R. P. (2015): spThin: an R package for spatial thinning of species occurrence records for use in ecological niche models. *Ecography* 38(5): 541-545.
- Baldwin, R.A. (2009): Use of maximum entropy modeling in wildlife research. *Entropy* 11(4): 854-866.
- Berg, L.S. (1949): The freshwater fishes of the USSR and adjacent countries, 4th ed., Part 3. *Adademia Nauk USSR, Moscow & Leningrad*. 927-1382 [in Russian].
- Blank, L., Blaustein, L. (2012): Using ecological niche modeling to predict the distributions of two endangered amphibian species in aquatic breeding sites. *Hydrobiologia* 685(1): 121-134.
- Blumenthal, D.M. (2006): Interactions between resource availability and enemy release in plant invasion. *Ecology Letters* 9 (7): 887-895.
- Bockstael, J. (1984): Spawning the Pumpkinseed Sunfish (*Lepomis gibbosus*) *American Currents* 10(5): 6-8.
- Boltachev, A.R., Danilyuk, O.N., Pakhorukov, N.V. (2003): Invasion of pumpkinseed sunfish *Lepomis macrochirus* (Perciformes, Centrarchidae) in inland reservoirs of Crimea. *Voprosi Ichtiologii* 43(6): 853-856.
- Britton, J.R., Cucherousset, J., Davies, G.D., Godard, M.J., Copp, G.H. (2010): Non-native fishes and climate change: predicting species responses to warming temperatures in a temperate region. *Freshwater Biology* 55: 1130-1141.
- Carlson, C.J. (2020): embarcadero: Species distribution modelling with Bayesian additive regression trees in R. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*. Early View: 1-9.
- Conrad, O., Bechtel, B., Bock, M., Dietrich, H., Fischer, E., Gerlitz, L., Wehberg, J., Wichmann, V., Böhner, J. (2015): System for Automated Geoscientific Analyses (SAGA) v. 2.1.4. *Geoscientific Model Development* 8: 1991-2007.
- Copp, G.H., Fox, M.G. (2007): Growth and life history traits of introduced pumpkinseed (*Lepomis gibbosus*) in Europe, and the relevance to invasiveness potential. pp. 289-306. In: Gherardi, F. (ed.), *Freshwater bioinvaders: profiles, distribution, and threats*. Springer, Berlin.
- Copp, G.H., Britton, J.R., Guo, Z., Ronni Edmonds-Brown, V., Pegg, J., Vilizzi, L., Davison, P.I. (2017): Trophic consequences of non-native pumpkinseed *Lepomis gibbosus* for native pond fishes. *Biological Invasions* 19: 25-41.
- Danylchuk, A.J., Fox, M.G. (1996): Size and age-related variation in the seasonal timing of nesting activity, nest characteristics, and female choice of parental male pumpkinseed sunfish (*Lepomis gibbosus*). *Canadian Journal of Zoology* 74: 1834-1840.
- Diripasko, O.A., Demchenko, N.A., Kulik, P.V., Zbroda, T.A. (2008): An Expansion of the Pumpkinseed, *Lepomis gibbosus* (Centrarchidae, Perciformes) Area of Distribution into the East of Ukraine. *Vestnik Zoologii*

- 42(3): 269-273.
- Demchenko, V.A., Demchenko, N.A. (2015): Alien species in the ichthyofauna of northwestern part of the Azov Sea basin. *Russian Journal of Biological Invasions* 6(2): 78-86.
- Domisch, S., Amatulli, G., Jetz, W. (2015): Near-global freshwater-specific environmental variables for biodiversity analyses in 1 km resolution. *Scientific Data* 2:150073.
- Dukes, J.S., Mooney, H.A. (1999): Does global change increase the success of biological invaders? *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 14(4): 135-139.
- Early, R., Bradley, B., Dukes, J., Lawler, J.J., Olden, J.D., Blumenthal, D.M., Gonzalez, P., Grosholz, E.D., Ibañez, I., Miller, L.P., Sorte, C.J.B., Tatem, A.J. (2016): Global threats from invasive alien species in the twenty-first century and national response capacities. *Nature Communications* 7: 12485.
- Elith, J., Leathwick, J.R. (2009): Species Distribution Models: Ecological Explanation and Prediction Across Space and Time. *Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution, and Systematics* 40(1): 677-697.
- Elith, J., Phillips, S.J., Hastie, T., Dudík, M., Chee, Y.E., Yates, C.J. (2011): A statistical explanation of MaxEnt for ecologists. *Diversity and Distributions* 11(1): 43-57.
- Fedonenko, E.V., Marenkov, O.N. (2013): Spreading, spatial distribution, and morphometric characteristics of the pumpkinseed sunfish *Lepomis gibbosus* (Centrarchidae, Perciformes) in the Zaporozhye Reservoir. *Russian Journal of Biological Invasions* 4(3): 194-199.
- Fick, S.E., Hijmans, R.J. (2017): WorldClim 2: new 1-km spatial resolution climate surfaces for global land areas. *International Journal of Climatology* 37: 4302-4315.
- FishBase (2022): World Wide Web electronic publication. Froese, R., Pauly, D. (eds.), <www.fishbase.org, accessed on 06.06.2022>.
- Fletcher, D. (2018): Biological invasion risk assessment, considering adaptation at multiple scale: The case of topmouth gudgeon *Pseudorasbora parva* (215 pp.). Thesis University of Montpellier.
- Fox, M.G. (1994): Growth, density, and interspecific influences on pumpkinseed sunfish life histories. *Ecology* 75(4): 1157-1171.
- Hammer, Ø., Harper, D.A.T., Ryan, P.D. (2001): PAST: Paleontological statistics software package for education and data analysis. *Palaeontologia Electronica* 4(1): 1-9.
- Hijmans, R.J., Phillips, S., Leathwick, J., Elith, J. (2011): Package 'dismo'. Available online at: <http://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/dismo/index.html>.
- Ilhéu, M., Matono, P., Bernardo, J.M. (2014): Invasibility of Mediterranean-climate rivers by non-native fish: the importance of environmental drivers and human pressures. *PLoS One* 9(11): e109694.
- Jakubčinová, K., Haruštiaková, D., Števo, B., Švolíková, K.S., Makovinská, J., Kováč, V. (2018): Distribution patterns and potential for further spread of three invasive fish species (*Neogobius melanostomus*, *Lepomis gibbosus* and *Pseudorasbora parva*) in Slovakia. *Aquatic Invasions* 13(4): 513-524.
- Keane, R.M., Crawley, M.J. (2002): Exotic plant invasions and the enemy release hypothesis. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 17(4):164-170.
- Keast, A., (1968): Feeding of some Great Lakes fishes at low temperatures. *Journal of the Fisheries Research Board of Canada* 25(6): 1199-1218.
- Kornis, M.S., Vander Zanden, M.J. (2010): Forecasting the distribution of the invasive round goby (*Neogobius melanostomus*) in Wisconsin tributaries to lake Michigan. *Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences* 67(3): 553.
- Kuhn, M. (2008): Building Predictive Models in R Using the caret Package. *Journal of Statistical Software* 28(5): 1-26.
- Kuybida, V.V., Nekrasova, O.D., Kutsokon, Y.K., Lopatynska, V.V. (2019): Summer fish kills in the Kaniv Reservoir. *Hydrobiological Journal* 55(1): 103-106.
- Kumar, S., Spaulding, S.A., Stohlgren, T.J., Hermann, K.A., Schmidt, T.S., Bahls, L.L. (2009): Potential habitat distribution for the freshwater diatom *Didymosphenia geminata* in the continental US. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment* 7(8): 415-420.
- Kursa, M.B., Jankowski, A., Rudnicki, W.R. (2010): Boruta - A system for Feature Selection. *Fundamenta Informaticae* 101: 271-285.
- Kutsokon, Y., Roman, A., Kvach, Y., Shcherbatiuk, M. (2021): Fish communities in three rivers of the South Podolia, Black Sea basin, Ukraine. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 73(3): 83-89.
- Lichstein, J.W., Simons, T.R., Shriver, S.A., Franzreb, K.E. (2002): Spatial autocorrelation and autoregressive models in ecology. *Ecological Monographs* 72(3): 445-463.
- GBIF (2021): *Lepomis gibbosus* (Linnaeus, 1758) GBIF.org (04 May 2021) GBIF Occurrence Download <https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.599axj>
- Loo, S.E., Nally, R.M., Lake, P.S. (2007). Forecasting New Zealand mudsnail invasion range: model comparisons using native and invaded ranges. *Ecological Applications* 17(1): 181-189.
- Marcus, H.C. (1932): The extent to which temperature changes influence-food consumption in large-mouth bass (*Iluro floridana*). *Transactions of the American Fisheries Society* 62: 202-210.
- Merow, C., Smith, M.J., Silander, J.A. Jr. (2013): A practical guide to MaxEnt for modeling species' distributions: what it does, and why inputs and settings matter. *Ecography* 36(10): 1058-1069.
- Milanovich, J.R., Peterman, W.E., Nibbelink, N.P., Maerz, J.C. (2010): Projected loss of a salamander diversity hotspot as a consequence of projected global climate change. *Plos One* 5(8): 12-189.
- Monkman, G.G., Kaiser, M.J., Hyder, K. (2018): Text and data mining of social media to map wildlife recreation activity. *Biological Conservation* 228: 89-99.
- Moorhouse, T.P., Macdonald, D.W. (2015): Are invasives worse in freshwater than terrestrial ecosystems?. *WIREs Water* 2: 1-8.
- Movchan, Yu.V., (2002): First find of pumpkinseed sunfish *Lepomis macrochirus* (Pisces, Centrarchidae) in the Yuzhnyi Bug river. *Vestnik Zoologii* 36(5): 84.
- Nakazato, T., Warren, D.L., Moyle, L.C. (2010): Ecological and geographic modes of species divergence in wild tomatoes. *American Journal of Botany* 97: 680-693.
- Nekrasova, O.D., Tytar, V.M., Kuybida, V.V. (2019): GIS modeling of climate change vulnerability of amphibians and reptiles in Ukraine. NAS of Ukraine, Shmalgausen Institute of Zoology NAS, Kyiv, Ukraine. [in Ukrainian].
- Nekrasova, O., Marushchak, O., Pupins, M., Skute, A., Tytar, V., Čeirāns, A. (2021a): Distribution and Potential Limiting Factors of the European Pond Turtle (*Emys orbicularis*) in Eastern Europe. *Diversity* 13(7): 280.
- Nekrasova, O., Tytar, V., Pupins, M., Čeirāns, A., Marushchak, O., Skute, A. (2021b): GIS Modeling Study of the Distribution of Viviparous Invasive Alien Fish Species in Eastern Europe in Terms of Global Climate Change, as Exemplified by *Poecilia reticulata* Peters, 1859 and *Gambusia holbrooki* Girard, 1859. *Diversity* 13(8), 385.
- Nekrasova, O., Tytar, V., Pupins, M., Čeirāns, A. (2022): Range expansion of the alien red-eared slider *Trachemys scripta* (Reptilia, Testudines) in Eastern Europe, with special reference to Latvia and Ukraine. *BioInvasions Records* 11(1): 287-295.
- Oksanen, J., Blanchet, F.G., Friendly, M., Kindt, R., Legendre, P., McGlinn, D., Minchin, P.R., O'Hara, R.B., Simpson, G.L., Solymos, P., Stevens, M.H.H., Szocs, E., Wagner, H. (2018): Vegan: Community ecology package. R package version 2.5-3. Retrieved from <http://CRAN.R-project.org/package=vegan>.
- Peterson, A.T., Soberón, J., Sánchez-Cordero, V. (1999): Conservatism of ecological niches in evolutionary time. *Science* 285: 1265-1267.
- Peterson, A., Soberón, J., Pearson, R., Anderson, R., Martínez-Meyer, E., Nakamura, M., Araujo, M. (2011): *Ecological Niches and Geographic Distributions*. Princeton University Press.
- Phillips, S.J., Anderson, R.P., Schapire, R.E. (2006): Maximum entropy modeling of species geographic distributions. *Ecological Modelling* 190(3-4): 231-259.
- Phillips, S.J., Dudík, M. (2008): Modeling of species distributions with Maxent: new extensions and a comprehensive evaluation. *Ecography* 31(2): 161-175.
- Pupina, A., Pupins, M., Nekrasova, O., Tytar, V., Kozynenko, I., Marushchak, O. (2018): Species Distribution Modelling: *Bombina bombina* (Linnaeus, 1761) and its Important Invasive Threat *Percottus glenii* (Dybowski, 1877) in Latvia under Global Climate Change. *Environmental Research, Engineering & Management* 74(4): 79-86.
- Radosavljevic, A., Anderson, R.P. (2014): Making better Maxent models of species distributions: complexity, overfitting and evaluation. *Journal of Biogeography* 41: 629-643.
- Rahel, F.J., Olden, J.D. (2008): Assessing the effects of climate change on aquatic invasive species. *Conservation Biology* 22(3): 521-533.
- Schweiger, O., Biesmeijer, J.C., Bommarco, R., Hickler, T., Hulme, P.E., Klotz, S., Kühn, I., Moora, M., Nielsen, A., Ohlemüller, R., Petanidou, T., Potts, S.G., Pyšek, P., Stout, J.C., Sykes, M.T., Tscheulin, T., Vilà, M., Walther, G.-R., Westphal, C., Winter, M., Zobel, M., Settele, J. (2010): Multiple stressors on biotic interactions: how climate change and alien species interact to affect pollination. *Biological Reviews* 85(4): 777-795.
- Stachowicz, J.J., Terwin, J.R., Whitlatch, R., Osman, R.W. (2002): Linking climate change and biological invasions: ocean warming facilitates nonindigenous species invasions. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 99(24): 15497-15500.
- Stefan, H.G., Preud'homme, E.B. (1993): Stream temperature estimation from air temperature. *Journal of the American Water Resources Association* 29 (1): 27-45.
- Sun, J., Harvey, H.H. (1986): Population dynamics of yellow perch (*Perca flavescens*) and pumpkinseed (*Lepomis gibbosus*) in two acid-stressed lakes. *Water, Air, and Soil Pollution*. 30: 611-617.
- Toivonen, T., Heikinheimo, V., Fink, C., Hausmann, A., Hiipala, T., Järvi, O., Tenkanen, H., Di Minin, E. (2019): Social media data for conservation science: A methodological overview. *Biological Conservation* 233: 298-315.
- Transboundary diagnostic study for the Dniester River Basin. (2005): United Nations Economic Commission for Europe. (Accessible at <https://www.osce.org/ukraine/104057>).
- Tytar, V.M., Nekrasova, O.D., Pupins, M., Čeirāns, A., Skute, A. 2021. Modelling the range expansion of pumpkinseed *Lepomis gibbosus* across Europe, with special focus on Latvia and Ukraine. pp. 112. In: Zhorov, D.G., Buga, S.V., Semenchenko, V.P., Petrašiūnas, D.A., Kolbas, A.P., Adamovich, B.V., Sinchuk, A.V. (eds.), *Book of Abstracts of the 1st International Scientific Conference: «Alien species of animals, fungi and plants in Belarus and*

- neighboring countries», Minsk, Belarus, March 23, 2021, Belarusian State University.
- Van Der Veer, G., Nentwig, W. (2015): Environmental and economic impact assessment of alien and invasive fish species in Europe using the generic impact scoring system. *Ecology of Freshwater Fish* 24: 646-656.
- Van Kleef, H., van der Velde, G., Leuven, R.S.E.W., Esselink, H. (2008): Pumpkinseed sunfish (*Lepomis gibbosus*) invasions facilitated by introductions and nature management strongly reduce macroinvertebrate abundance in isolated water bodies. *Biological Invasions* 10: 1481-1490.
- Vignali, S., Barras, A.G., Arlettaz, R., Braunisch, V. (2020): SDMtune: An R package to tune and evaluate species distribution models. *Ecology and Evolution* 10(20): 11488-11506.
- Vinogradov, K.O. (1960): Ichthyofauna of the North-Western Part of the Black Sea. Publisher Academy of Sciences URSR, Kyiv. [In Ukrainian].
- Walther, G.R., Roques, A., Hulme, P.E., Sykes, M.T., Pyšek, P., Kühn, I., Zobel, M., Bacher, S., Botta-Dukát, S., Bugmann, H., Czucz, B., Dauber, J., Hickler, T., Jarošík, V., Kenis, M., Klotz, S., Minchin, D., Moora, M., Nentwig, W., Ott, J., Panov V.E., Reineking, B., Robinet, C., Semenchenko, V., Solarz, W., Thuiller, W., Vilà, M., Vohland, K., Settele, J. (2009): Alien species in a warmer world: risks and opportunities. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 24(12): 686-693.
- Wenger, S.J., Isaak, D.J., Luce, C.H., Nevillea, H.M., Fausch, K.D., Dunham, J.B., Dauwalter D.C., Young, M.K., Elsner, M.M., Rieman, B.E., Hamlet, A.F., Williams, J.E. (2011): Flow regime, temperature, and biotic interactions drive differential declines of trout species under climate change. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 108(34): 14175-14180.
- Yavno, S., Gobin, J., Wilson, C.C., Vila-Gispert, A., Copp, G.H., Fox, M.G. (2020): New and Old World phylogeography of pumpkinseed *Lepomis gibbosus* (Linnaeus, 1758): the North American origin of introduced populations in Europe. *Hydrobiologia* 847: 345-364.
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